

THE CONCEPT OF LEADERSHIP AND ITS ROLE AND ROLE IN THE
DEVELOPMENT OF SOCIETY

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Annotation: the article reveals the essence of leadership, reveals that a person succumbs to the feeling of helplessness, seizes the control of reality around him, and his personality disintegrates. The article sets out recommendations on how, in a society dominated by such uncertainty, to independently fulfill the necessary resources in the implementation of the goals that they set, to preserve their values. It is clearly shown that the human position, the growth of his ability to self - development-is set against the level of authoritarian and commanding character.

Keywords: Leader, Leader, ability, authoritarian leader, Democratic leader, liberal leader

A leader or leader is a person who wants others to follow his Trends and ideas. It is also possible to temporarily achieve leadership, but the true leader is distinguished by irreplaceable loyalty by the next steps forward.

Each leader or chief is individual and irreversible in his own way. This is due to the fact that each boss organizes his work activities, managerial activities in his own way. One problem that has been studied in detail in the field of Management in political psychology is the different management styles. German scientists in this field G.Gibsh and M. Forverg, Russian scientist V.D. Parigin, L.N.Umansky, M.Yu. The work of Zhukov and others is especially noteworthy. Summarizing all scientific research, let's give a characteristic to the three main management methods adopted in Social Psychology. These three styles are authoritarian, democratic and liberal styles of work.

An authoritarian leader conveys all instructions to employees in a spirit of workmanship, in a clear, sharp tone. In the process of communication, too, it uses strict tones, such as an exclamation towards employees, a sharp ban. One of his main goals is to pass his sentence, whatever the way it is. His speech is also clear and fluent always in a serious tone. Praising or punishing employees over a case, criticizing them is purely subjective, and this thing depends on the mood of the boss and his personal attitude towards those individuals. The wishes of the members of the team, their opinions and advice are taken into account only in very few cases, in most cases such wishes or instructions are limited or unsatisfied by direct insults, humiliation or moral punishment. Such a leader usually keeps a secret from the team how he wants to carry out his work methods, future plans, some specific work, Opera, which, in his opinion, can negatively affect his reputation.

The authoritarian leader has visions of the abilities of each team member, their attitude to work, their position, according to which he has programmed the work actions of each employee in the maximum possible way, in which any restrictions bring his open anger, and for this he has different methods of punishment. That is, in such communities, power is centralized, the head of the community is the sole governor of this center-that is why phrases from the tribe "my people", "my work", "according to my opinion" are often used here. Such leaders have such self-sacrifice towards their work that they cannot imagine themselves without work, that is, the work "covered his whole body". For this reason, such a leader knows every person very well about his daily work activities, his results.

But, in fact, he is more interested in his leadership role, leadership there than in the content of his work, and gives himself an assessment of those qualities. Since this quality naturally affects both the quality of the work and the quantity of the work, not all the tasks set before the team are completed ("Iron Leader"). In such communities, the work of criticism is rather sluggish, since it does not allow both itself and others to criticize. To criticize, in his opinion, only the chief is entitled. At meetings, starting the word itself and not giving the initiative to others to the end, people's suggestions, their feelings are ignored.

G. Gibsh and M. Forvergs analyze that the efficiency of the work in which the authoritarian leader is the head is much higher, and that the production indicators will also be higher. But the mental-spiritual atmosphere in the community was heavy, tangy, and this thing led to a person's dissatisfaction with the community, with work. People who work in labor communities headed by such a leader can easily replace their professions, jobs.

The Democratic leader, on the contrary, is in favor of giving independence, work to subordinates. Distributes when giving assignments at work, taking into account the personal abilities of workers. In doing so, he also takes into account the personal inclinations of employees. Orders or assignments are usually given in the sense of an offer. His speech is simple, always calm, quiet, in which a friendly, friendly attitude is felt. Praising a person, increasing his position or assessing his work according to the shortcomings in the work is always carried out in agreement with the opinion of the team members. Criticism, often in the form of suggestion, desire, is conveyed to the "culprit" as an assessment of the content of what is done. Therefore, its spatial-social state is "within the community".

Criticism and self-criticism in the team are set in such a way that no one suffers from its consequences. Because more often than not a boss, but other activists of the team-informal leaders-criticize. The chief is not afraid to make a mistake-to take the shortcomings in front of the public. Because the sense of responsibility in it is felt not only during communication with members of higher management organizations, but also communication with employees, and loves to divide responsibility for the assigned task into others. The chief has no secret from his staff, so even at meetings more and more he speaks, and not all employees, he fully uses the right to make the final decision and complete the words, to generalize.

According to the analyzes of Gibsch and Forvergs, the spiritual and spiritual atmosphere in the communities led by such a chief is very good, workers are satisfied with the team, work, there are few cases of leaving-he, but the production will hardly be normal.

It is difficult to know whether the attitude of a leader who works in a Liberal (loyalist) style to work is satisfied with the work or not. In it, prohibition is not punishable-instead it is often limited to acquaintance with the final outcome of the case only. The problems of the team of the team of a great leader who is not interested in the highs and lows of work, seem to be walking in another "universe". It does not give clear quotations, instead the tasks that must be done through informal leaders or those close to it are conveyed to the executors. His main task, in his eyes, is to create working conditions for employees, eliminate shortcomings in work, find the necessary products, supplies, attend meetings and hokazo.

When he has to communicate with employees, he is always a hushmumomala, trying not to violate the norms of etiquette, morality, but never arguing with them. At meetings, if a problem causes a discussion, it leaves the last word to itself, not directly interfering with the process. Thus the employees were given freedom of thought and action.

Even if the chief is asked for his opinion on those free actions, it is not clear from him, because he does not know the employees well, he is afraid to offend the rest. His spatial-psychological state is "outside the group".

Scientists believe that in the communities where such a leader conducted the work, all indicators are always behind, and I do not even land. The Liberal leader tries to look for work from elsewhere, without standing too much, by doing anarchy at work.

The management styles evaluated above are more leadership-specific than leadership-but, in the scientific literature, both of these phrases are often used synonymously. In fact, the best leader will also embody all leadership qualities in himself. Because the leader in a purely social psychological sense is more manifested in himself in different conditions, which is differentiated according to personal qualities. For example, the leader is the organizer, the leader is the initiator, the leader is the erudite, the team is the leader who manages the emotional-emotional state, the leader is the wrist and the hokoza. A good leader, knowing these qualities of a leader, must educate them in himself and be able to work in collaboration with leaders in his team.

Experts indicate that there are four main contextual factors that leaders should be aware of when assessing the situation. These factors include:

1. Leaders should consider the relationship between group leaders and members. Social and interdependent factors can play an important role in determining which approach is best. For example, a group that lacks efficiency and productivity can use a style that emphasizes order, rules, and clearly defined roles. An effective group of highly skilled workers can use a more democratic style that allows group members to work independently and make organizational decisions.

2. The leader must decide for himself his task. Tasks can vary from simple to complex, but it is necessary to clearly define the task in order to determine whether the leader has been successfully and competently completed.

3. The level of authority of the leader over the members of the group should also be considered. Some leaders have potential in their position, such as making fire, doing work, rewarding, or obeying them. Other leaders often gain power through relationships with employees, often respecting them, helping them and helping them get involved in the decision-making process.

4. Everything-the Blanchard model assumes that leaders must take into account the maturity level of each group member. Maturity levels are the ability and willingness of an individual to complete a task. Incapacitated, but appointment to a member fails.

In conclusion, as a result of research in Moscow and other large centers in recent years, it has come to the conclusion that in reality it is difficult to meet a purely democratic or purely authoritarian leader in life, but even when they are encountered, it turns out that they cannot control a team for a long time. That is why they depend on the situation, the situation, the concrete community, the norms of behavior adopted in it, the idea that interpersonal relationships determine the tactics and style of work of both the tipii leader and the leader. But the practical importance of knowing the psychological content and essence of these leadership styles is that each style has its own positive side, while the skillful leader is self-educated, it is advisable for them to educate the most optimal, especially those suitable for the team he leads.

LIST OF LITERATURE USED:

1. Urinov, Sh K. "THE MAIN CRITERIA OF CULTURAL CENTERS IN THE FORMATION OF CREATIVE ABILITY." *Multidisciplinary Journal of Science and Technology* 3.5 (2023): 52-59.

2. KO'rinov, Sh, and G. Bozorboyeva. "MADANIYAT SOHASIDA PABLIK RILEYSHNZ (JAMOATCHILIK BILAN ALOQALAR) VA REKLAMA." *TECHNICAL SCIENCE RESEARCH IN UZBEKISTAN* 1.4 (2023): 217-224.
3. O'rinov, SH K., and E. Sultonmurodova. "MENEJERNING MADANIYAT SOHASIDAGI KASBIY MALAKASI, USLUBLARI VA REJALASHTIRISH." *TECHNICAL SCIENCE RESEARCH IN UZBEKISTAN* 1.4 (2023): 225-230.
4. KO'rinov, Sh. "LOYIHA MENEJMENTINING ASOSIY TAMOYILLARI." *TECHNICAL SCIENCE RESEARCH IN UZBEKISTAN* 1.4 (2023): 136-143.
5. Ne'matullayeva, Sh. "MADANIYAT MARKAZLARINING PROFESSIONAL JAMOALAR BILAN HAMKORLIKNI TASHKIL ETISH MASALALARI." *Педагогика и психология в современном мире: теоретические и практические исследования* 2.3 (2023): 25-29.
6. KO'rinov, Sh, and S. Sadullayeva. "MUZEYSHUNOSLIK ISTIQBOLLARI." *IJODKOR O'QITUVCHI* 3.26 (2023): 97-101.
7. Orinov, Sh K., and S. Rozimurodova. "Maqom San'atiga E'tibor Milliy San'atimizga E'tibor." "ONLINE-CONFERENCES" PLATFORM. 2023.
8. O'rinov, Sh K., and G. Halimova. "HAVASKORLIK BADIY JAMOALARI TUSHUNCHASI VA FUNKSIONAL VAZIFASI." *INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCES*. Vol. 1. No. 2. 2023.
9. KORinov, Sh, and M. Ismoilova. "BOSHQARUV KONSEPSIYASI VA ASOSIY TUSHUNCHALAR." *PEDAGOGS jurnali* 26.2 (2023): 62-64.
10. KORinov, Sh, and M. Hasanova. "BOSHQARUV MADANIYATI TARKIBI FUNKSIYALARI MEZONLARI-MADANIYAT MARKAZLARI MISOLIDA." *PEDAGOGS jurnali* 26.2 (2023): 65-66.
11. KORinov, Sh, and M. Habibullayeva. "ART MENEJER–MARKETING FAOLIYATINING ASOSIY YO'NALISHLARI SIFATIDA." *PEDAGOGS jurnali* 26.2 (2023): 59-61.
12. KORinov, Sh, and N. Jahongirova. "O'ZBEKISTONDA TEATR FAOLIYATIDA MARKETINGNING RIVOJLANISHI." *PEDAGOGS jurnali* 26.1 (2023): 161-162.
13. KORinov, Sh, and M. Raupova. "BOZOR IQTISODIYOTI SHAROITIDA MUZEYLARNING RIVOJLANISH XUSUSIYATLARI." *PEDAGOGS jurnali* 26.1 (2023): 116-118.
14. KORinov, Sh. "NOANANAVIY MAYDON TOMOSHA DRAMATURGIYASIDA INVERSIYA USLUBI, KOMPOZITSION BIRLIK ASOSI." *PEDAGOGS jurnali* 26.1 (2023): 113-115.
15. O'rinov, Sh K., and G. A. Nurilloeva. "TASVIRIY SAN'AT MARKETINGINI RIVOJLANTIRISH MASALALARI." *INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCES*. Vol. 1. No. 1. 2023.
16. O'rinov, Sh K., and X. Abduraxmonova. "MADANIYAT VA SAN'AT SOHASIDAGI BOSHQARUVNING O 'ZIGA XOS XUSUSIYATLARI." *PEDAGOG* 6.1 (2023): 226-231.
17. Orinov, Sh K., and S. Boboqulova. "MADANIYAT VA SAN'AT BOSHQARUVINING BUGUNGI KUNDAGI AHAMIYATI." *ta'lim va rivojlanish tahlili onlayn ilmiy jurnali* (2022): 78-82.
18. Orinov, Sh K., and N. Sadridinova. "MADANIYAT MARKAZLARIGA AHOLINI JALB ETISH OMILLARI." *TA'LIM VA RIVOJLANISH TAHLILI ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI* (2022): 123-129.

19. Orinov, Sh K., and E. Sultonmurodova. "XALQ OG'ZAKI IJODINING TARIXIY TARAQQIYOTI." *TALIM VA RIVOJLANISH TAHLILI ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI* (2022): 166-172.
20. Orinov, Sh K., and M. Rahmatova. "MADANIYAT VA SAN'AT MUASSASALARINI BOSHQARISHDA IJRO INTIZOMINI TATBIQ ETISH MASALALARI." *TALIM VA RIVOJLANISH TAHLILI ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI* (2022): 130-135.
21. Ражабов, Т. И. (2020). Тическая классификация узбекской детской народной музыки и игр. Наука, образование и культура, (3 (47)), 61-63.
22. Ражабов, Т. И., & Ибодов, У. Р. (2020). Обеспечение национального наследия в обучении песням бухарского детского фольклора на уроках музыки. Вестник науки и образования, (21-2 (99)), 55-58.
23. Ражабов, Т. И. (2021). Усовершенствование научно-методических возможностей обучения бухарским детским фольклорным песням в средней общеобразовательной школе. Наука, техника и образование, (2-2 (77)), 84-86.
24. Ражабов, Т. И. (2020). Педагогические возможности использования детских фольклорных песен в духовно-нравственном воспитании младших школьников. Вестник науки и образования, (5-2 (83)), 34-37.
25. Ражабов, Т. И. (2019). Описание вековых ценностей в песне "туговое дерево-балх" и его место в воспитании учащейся молодежи. In Россия-Узбекистан. Международные образовательные и социально-культурные технологии: векторы развития (pp. 70-71).
26. Ражабов, Д. З., & Ражабов, Т. И. (2018). Формирование и развитие узбекской народной лирики. In Международная образовательная деятельность как фактор развития и сотрудничества высших учебных заведений в современном поликультурном мире (pp. 207-212).
27. Ражабов, Т. И. (2023). Совершенствование Механизма Духовно-Нравственного Формирования Учащихся Через Узбекские Народные Песни. *Miasto Przyszłości*, 33, 167-176.
28. Ражабов, Т. И. (2021). Ўқувчи-ёшларга ўзбек миллий мусиқа фольклори намуналари воситасида эстетик тарбия бериш. *Science and Education*, 2(11), 1094-1103.
29. Тўхтасин, Р. И. (2022). ЎЗБЕК ХАЛҚ ҚЎШИҚЛАРИ ВА ИЖРОЛАРИ ҲАҚИДА. *Central Asian Research Journal for Interdisciplinary Studies (CARJIS)*, (Special issue), 64-71.
30. Rajabov, T. I. The Mechanism of Teaching Uzbek Musical Folklore. *Procedia of Philosophical and Pedagogical Sciences ISSN, 2795(546X)*,
31. Ражабов, Т. (2023). О 'zbek bolalar musiqiy o 'yin folklorining mavzuviy tasnifi. *Общество и инновации*, 4(5/S), 340-345.
32. Ражабов, Т. И. (2022). Совершенствование Механизма Духовно-Нравственного Формирования Учащихся Через Народные Музыка И Песни. *Miasto Przyszłości*, 29, 363-367.
33. Rajabov, T. I. (2023). Distinctive Features of Folk Songs that Serve in the Spiritual and Moral Formation of Bukhara Pupils. *Pioneer: Journal of Advanced Research and Scientific Progress*, 2(3), 59-68.
34. Rajabov, T. I. (2022). The role of bukhara folklore songs in youth education in the system of continuous education.
35. Rajabov, T. I. The Mechanism of Teaching Uzbek Musical Folklore. *Procedia of Philosophical and Pedagogical Sciences ISSN, 2795(546X)*, 1
36. Rajabov, T. I. (2023). Distinctive Features of Folk Songs that Serve in the Spiritual and Moral Formation of Bukhara Pupils. *Pioneer: Journal of Advanced Research and Scientific Progress*, 2(3), 59-68.

37. Madrimov, B. K., & Rajabov, T. I. (2022). Uzbek Ceremonial Folklore and its Characteristics. Nexus: Journal of Advances Studies of Engineering Science, 1(4), 53-56.
38. Rajabov, T. (2022). UZLUKSIZ TA'LIM TIZIMIDA O'ZBEK MUSIQA FOLKLORINI O'RGATISH DOLZARAB PEDAGOGIK MUAMMO SIFATIDA. IJODKOR O'QITUVCHI, 2(21), 21-31.
39. Ibovovich, T. R. (2022). PRACTICAL SITUATION OF TEACHING UZBEK MUSICAL FOLKLORE IN THE CONTINUOUS EDUCATION SYSTEM. International Journal of Early Childhood Special Education, 14(6).
40. Ibovovich, R. T. (2021). EDUCATIONAL IMPORTANCE OF CHILDREN'S FOLKLORE SONGS IN MUSIC CULTURE CLASSES. Thematics Journal of Arts and Culture, 5(1).
41. Равшан, Расулов Рауфович. "ЗАМОНАВИЙ БАЙРАМЛАР РЕЖИССУРАСИДА ХАЛҚ ИЖОДИ НАМУНАЛАРИ ТАЪСИРЧАН ВОСИТА СИФАТИДА." ТА'LIM VA RIVOJLANISH TANHLILI ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI (2022): 117-122.
42. Равшан, Расулов Рауфович. "ТЕАТР ТОМОШАЛАРИДА ТАЪСИРЧАН ВОСИТАЛАРДАН ФОЙДАЛАНИШ УСУЛЛАРИ." ТА'LIM VA RIVOJLANISH TANHLILI ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI (2022): 145-151.
43. Расулов, Равшан. "ЗАМОНАВИЙ БАЙРАМЛАР РЕЖИССУРАСИДА ТАЪСИРЧАН ВОСИТАЛАРНИНГ ТУТГАН УРНИ ВА АХАМИЯТИ." TECHNICAL SCIENCE RESEARCH IN UZBEKISTAN 1.4 (2023): 36-46.
44. Взгляды восточных мыслителей на узбекскую народную музыку. У.Х. Рамазонова Multidisciplinary Journal of Science and Technology 3(5), 45-46
45. 45. Holmurodovna R. U. I., Oqila S. Makom art is a priority in the musical culture of Uzbekistan // Проблемы педагогики. – 2020. – №. 2 (47). – С. 87-88.
46. 46. Kholmurodovna R. U., Obidovna R. M. Social norms, sanctions and personality // Вестник науки и образования. – 2020. – №. 21-2(99). – С. 115-118.
47. 47. Рамазонова У.Х., Сайфуллаева О.М. Развитие чувств у детей // Проблемы науки. – 2021. – №. 1(60). – С. 49-51.
48. 48. Ramazonova U. X., Esanova M. J. An'anaviy xonandalik rivojida maqomlarning o'rni // Science and Education. – 2022. – Т. 3. – №. 1. – С. 496-501.
49. 49. Ramazonova O. K., qizi Mustaqimova G. G. Formation and Development of National Musical Traditions // European journal of innovation in nonformal education. – 2022. – Т. 2. – №. 1. – С. 336-339.
50. 50. Рамазонова Ў. Х. ТАЛАБАЛАРДА МАЪНАВИЙ-АХЛОҚИЙ ТУШУНЧАЛАРНИ ШАКЛЛАНТИРИШ, ГУРУХ БИЛАН ИШЛАШ ВА УНИ БОШҚАРИШ ТАМОЙИЛЛАРИ.
51. 51. Kholmurodovna U. R. Formation of publicistic performing skills in singing. – 2021.
52. 52. Рамазонова У.Х., Эсанова М.Ж. ПОДГОТОВКА МОЛОДЫХ ПЕВЦОВ
53. 53. КАНСАМБЛЕВ ОМУВЫСТУПЛЕНИЮ // Наука, техника и образование. – 2021. – №. 2-1. – С. 88-91.
54. 54. Ramazonova U. H., Muhamadova M. The spiritual impact of traditional sound exercises on the minds of students. – 2022.
55. 55. Ramazonova O. K., Shukurov M. Historical development of status. – 2022.
56. 56. Features of Sound Recording in the Uzbek Singing Art
57. 57. U H Ramazonova. Procedia of Philosophical and Pedagogical Sciences ISSN 2795 (546X),